

An Explainable Active Learning Approach for Enhanced Defect Detection in Manufacturing

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Abstract. Artificial Intelligence (AI) can significantly support manufacturing companies in their pursuit of operational excellence, by maintaining efficiency while minimizing defects. However, the complexity of AI solutions often creates a barrier to their practical application. Transparency and user-friendliness should be prioritized to ensure that the insights generated by AI can be effectively applied in real-time decision-making.

To bridge this gap and foster a collaborative environment where AI and human expertise collectively drive operational excellence, this paper suggests an AI approach that targets identifying defects in production while providing understandable insights. A semi-supervised convolutional neural network (CNNs) with attention mechanisms and Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) for explainable active learning is discussed. Predictions but also feedback from human experts are used to dynamically adjust the learning focus, ensuring a continuous improvement cycle in defect detection capabilities. The proposed approach has been tested in a use case related to the manufacturing of batteries. Preliminary results demonstrate substantial improvements in prediction accuracy and operational efficiency, offering a scalable solution for industrial applications aiming at zero defects.

Keywords: Active learning · Defect detection · Explainable AI · Manufacturing

1 Introduction

Quality control is an integral part of manufacturing systems [1]. Traditionally, it has been a manual process heavily dependent on operators' expertise [2], and often prone to errors. Experience tends to reduce the frequency of such errors, but it is something hard to transfer [3].

Nowadays, Machine and Deep Learning approaches can be used to automate quality control and predict a defect, by identifying abnormalities in process data. This in turn may reduce defects and resources wasted in the processing of defective products [5].

Nevertheless, AI models, becoming increasingly complex, are, in a similar way, increasingly considered as black boxes, difficult to understand and, subsequently, to trust. This requires the introduction of methods to explain their operations and outputs [4].

Hence, this paper investigates the combination of an LRP layer to increase the explainability of a CNN model adopted for the identification of defects in a product's 2D images. In addition, a human feedback mechanism is introduced to allow the operators to verify the result of the AI model and label new defect types, thus improving the efficiency of the CNN model over time.

2 Literature Review

AI approaches have been extensively used in manufacturing for scenarios like quality control [6] or predictive maintenance [7]. In [6] a CNN-based algorithm is presented that identifies product defects. Such approaches have also been presented in [8] where the importance of computer vision techniques is explored. Similarly, in [9] a survey on machine and deep learning techniques is conducted aiming to improve and automate the quality control process in manufacturing.

Despite these advancements, and despite the availability of advanced deployment approaches targeting AI systems [10, 11], AI deployment on the shop floor often encounters resistance, primarily due to the complexity of these systems [12]. One of the main reasons is the lack of explainability [13]. While the transparency of AI models and their output is important to ensure human trust in AI, especially those constructed around the use of advanced machine and deep learning techniques, it is often challenging or non-existent [14]. This in turn hinders the application, by shopfloor personnel, of AI-generated results that can improve quality control in real-world environments [15].

Explainable AI (XAI) aims to address these issues by making AI decisions more comprehensible and justifiable. XAI techniques fall into two categories: transparent approaches [16–19], which are inherently interpretable models like decision trees, and post hoc approaches [20, 21], which include both model-specific methods and model-agnostic techniques like SHAP [22] and LIME [23], offering explanations after model training. The potential of XAI to improve quality control is particularly significant in settings that rely heavily on human-AI collaboration. By making AI models more interpretable, XAI allows line operators to understand model uncertainties while enhancing their ability to interact effectively with AI tools [24, 25]. However, the literature indicates a gap in systems that facilitate active feedback from operators to AI models; essential to prevent model drift and to continuously refine AI tools [26].

Active learning is reshaping AI in manufacturing by employing techniques like ensemble methods and contextual bandits, which strategically use informative samples to enhance learning processes [27]. Additionally, uncertainty sampling and selective data querying help AI adapt quickly to new defects and changes in manufacturing, merging operator feedback into training cycles. This fosters a collaborative and adaptive learning environment crucial for achieving zero-defect manufacturing goals [28, 29].

3 Approach

In the study, the primary goal is the introduction of an approach (Fig. 1) that combines advanced AI algorithms, with XAI coupled with a human feedback collection mechanism, to adjust the learning focus of the algorithm dynamically.

A CNN algorithm is selected, due to its versatility and high customizability. The objective of the CNN algorithm is the classification of an image representing a product's surface, based on the presence or absence of a defect. The task of identifying defects is translated into a classification problem due to the simplicity of the image labelling approach in comparison to the complex labelling approach in object detection-related tasks; thus, facilitating the active learning application of the approach.

Subsequently, LRP is applied on top of the CNN model to generate explanations of the outputs of the model. Based on the reviewed literature, and due to the inner complexity of the CNN, LRP is selected. A feedback pipeline is constructed that aims to use the operator's feedback to actively retrain the CNN model.

In more detail, the approach is structured around 8 consecutive steps, which are presented hereafter.

- **Step 1 – CNN model construction:** Images are categorised as defective or non-defective, forming the training dataset for the CNN, which is then deployed for real-time defect detection on the shop floor.
- **Step 2 – LRP rule selection:** After CNN development, the LRP- γ rule is added to introduce an explainable AI layer.
- **Step 3 – Forward pass:** Images pass through the CNN, storing intermediate activations and weights.
- **Step 4 – Relevance initialisation:** Relevance at the output layer is set based on the defect presence classification.
- **Step 5 – Backward relevance propagation:** The relevance score is propagated backwards through the model's network. For each layer of the model, the LRP rule redistributes the relevance from the output layer to the input layer. To achieve this, the LRP- γ rule uses the dimensionless formula detailed in (1).

$$R_j = \sum_i \frac{a_j(w_{ij} + \gamma w_{ij}^+)}{\sum_k a_k(w_{ik} + \gamma w_{ik}^+)} R_i \quad (1)$$

where:

- R_j : The relevance score for a neuron j in the current layer of the model,
- R_i : The relevance score for a neuron i in the next layer of the model,
- a_j : The activation of neuron j in the current layer of the model,
- w_{ij} : The weight connecting neuron j in the current layer to neuron i ,
- γ : The Gamma parameter that scales the positive part of the weight,
- $\sum_k a_k(w_{ik} + \gamma w_{ik}^+)$: The normalisation term.

Using the backward propagation results the LRP can generate the necessary explanations which are then provided to the feedback interface, making them easily accessible to an operator. The approach concludes with the following three steps.

- **Step 6 – Operator feedback collection:** Operators use a user-friendly interface to review LRP-generated explanations in real-time, providing feedback (OK or NOK) and identifying potential new defect types. Operators can select between three options (OK, NOK and New class), which is recorded and the classification given by the operators is stored.

- **Step 7 – Feedback collection:** Based on the provided feedback, the dataset is updated in an automated manner weekly. The dataset will be updated to include newly labelled images in existing classes, while new classes are dynamically created based on the users’ feedback.
- **Step 8 – Active learning:** Ultimately, CNN is periodically retrained with the updated dataset, improving its predictive accuracy and adapting to new defect types based on the production cycle time.

Fig. 1. Active learning approach based on XAI and operator’s feedback.

4 Use Case

The proposed approach was applied to a laser welding process in battery module assembly. High-resolution images captured by a 2D vision-based system served as the primary data source, processed on a computing infrastructure consisting of an Intel Core i7-13700H processor and an NVIDIA RTX A1000 GPU. For the initial training of the CNN, a dataset of 1800 mixed real-world and synthetic images was used, enhancing the model’s exposure to rare defects. The CNN (Fig. 2), utilized the Adam optimizer, binary cross entropy loss and 10 epochs for better defect detection accuracy.

The CNN model has been trained using the initial 1800 2D images. The CNN model’s architecture can be seen in Fig. 2. The performance of the initial CNN model can be seen in Table 1, evaluated using the accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score [30].

LRP was applied to the CNN’s outputs to generate explainable visual data, assisting operators in understanding and validating defect detections, as seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. The architecture of the CNN model.

Fig. 3. (a) LRP results presented to an operator along with original images and (b) feedback collection interface (grey overlay added on top of real-time data due to data confidentiality).

As seen in Fig. 3, the LRP colourises in red the pixels of an image where defects are not present, while pixels in blue indicate the presence of the class characterising defects. By presenting the original and explained images next to each other, the operator can visually identify defects detected by the CNN. Due to the nature of the battery manufacturing process, defects, such as spots on the weld, can be small, further complicating the manual inspection process. Nevertheless, due to the minute size of the defects, images that contain products with defective welding can potentially be misclassified.

Feedback is collected by operators to actively improve CNN's performance. Feedback provided directly labels the under-examination image with either OK (representing the absence of defect) or NOK (representing the existence of defect). Operators are given a third option to introduce new labels in the dataset in cases where after manual inspection of the under-examination battery a new type of defect is uncovered.

A controlled experiment conducted over a week gathered substantial feedback, leading to the retraining of the CNN, whose performance can be seen in Table 1.

Post-retraining, improvements were observed: accuracy increased marginally from 0.89 to 0.9, while recall improved from 0.57 to 0.66, and the F1-score from 0.70 to 0.77, indicating enhanced reliability and reduced risk of missing defects.

The results presented in Table 1 underline the importance of enabling operators to provide feedback on data they utilise daily to ensure that quality standards are met. Given

Table 1. Performance comparison of original and retrained CNN model.

Metric	Original CNN	Retrained CNN
Accuracy	0.89	0.9
Precision	0.94	0.94
Recall	0.57	0.66
F1-score	0.70	0.77

the rapid digitalisation of today's manufacturing, AI systems are adopted and operators are faced with the challenge of understanding the results produced by them. With the application of XAI, operators demonstrated an increased reliance on the outputs of the CNN, given the explanations the LRP layer provided them. On top of this, the integration of humans in the loop of continuous model improvement is an effective approach given the increase in the CNN model's performance; thus, validating the effectiveness of integrating active learning and XAI in manufacturing environments.

Lastly, operators were asked to provide feedback on the usefulness of introducing explainability to the AI system. Approximately 83% of operators (7 men and 5 women) deemed the introduction of explainability as useful since it allows them to become part of the constant improvement process and speed up the manual defect identification phase, while the rest pointed out that improvements should be made to the feedback interface to increase its user-friendliness, such as removing pop-up dialogues and incorporating the feedback options beneath the model's output.

5 Conclusion

This study presents an approach for detecting subtle defects in battery module assembly lines, utilizing a semi-supervised CNN for initial defect detection. LRP is then applied to the CNN's outputs to visually explain the decision-making process, pinpointing why specific areas are flagged as defective, enhancing transparency and supporting the validation of detected defects, thus, providing clarity in quality control processes.

Operators evaluate areas highlighted by LRP to confirm defect identifications and to uncover new types of defects. This is essential for periodic retraining of the CNN, enabling the system to adapt to evolving manufacturing conditions and continuously refine its accuracy. This dynamic approach has been tested in a battery modules assembly use case with its result demonstrating the potential to improve defect detection but also to establish a robust mechanism for enhancement of quality control practices.

Future research will be focused on further optimising the active learning pipeline and expanding the areas of application of the proposed approach through the adoption of the LRP layer on more diverse manufacturing scenarios. Also, future research will aim to extend the approach to account for the uncertainty of defects in the process of feedback collection by operators to assist them during the feedback collection phase.

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References

1. Chryssolouris, G.: *Manufacturing Systems: Theory and Practice*. Springer, New York (2006)
2. Medici, V., et al.: Integration of non-destructive inspection (NDI) systems for zero-defect manufacturing in the industry 4.0 era. In: *2023 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Industry 4.0 & IoT (MetroInd4.0&IoT)*, pp. 439–444. IEEE, Brescia, Italy (2023)
3. Torres, Y., Nadeau, S., Landau, K.: Classification and quantification of human error in manufacturing: a case study in complex manual assembly. *Appl. Sci.* **11**, 749 (2021)
4. Ntoulmperis, M., et al.: 3D point cloud analysis for surface quality inspection: a steel parts use case. *Procedia CIRP* **122**, 509–514 (2024)
5. Jia, Z., Wang, M., Zhao, S.: A review of deep learning-based approaches for defect detection in smart manufacturing. *J. Opt.* **53**, 1345–1351 (2024)
6. Sundaram, S., Zeid, A.: Artificial intelligence-based smart quality inspection for manufacturing. *Micromachines* **14**, 570 (2023)
7. Cerquitelli, T., Nikolakis, N., O’Mahony, N., Macii, E., Ippolito, M., Makris, S. (eds.): *Predictive Maintenance in Smart Factories: Architectures, Methodologies, and Use-cases*. Springer Singapore, Singapore (2021)
8. Andrianandrianina Johanesa, T.V., Equeter, L., Mahmoudi, S.A.: Survey on AI applications for product quality control and predictive maintenance in industry 4.0. *Electronics* **13**, 976 (2024)
9. Mueller, C., Mezhyuev, V.: AI models and methods in automotive manufacturing: a systematic literature review. In: *AI-Emran, M., Shaalan, K. (eds.) Recent Innovations in Artificial Intelligence and Smart Applications*, pp. 1–25. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2022)
10. Nikolakis, N., et al.: A microservice architecture for predictive analytics in manufacturing. *Procedia Manuf.* **51**, 1091–1097 (2020)
11. Bowden, D., et al.: A cloud-to-edge architecture for predictive analytics
12. Gabsi, A.E.H.: Integrating artificial intelligence in industry 4.0: insights, challenges, and future prospects—a literature review. *Ann. Oper. Res.* (2024)
13. Felderer, M., Ramler, R.: Quality assurance for AI-based systems: overview and challenges (introduction to interactive session). In: *Winkler, D., Biffel, S., Mendez, D., Wimmer, M., Bergsmann, J. (eds.) Software Quality: Future Perspectives on Software Engineering Quality*, pp. 33–42. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2021)
14. Walmsley, J.: Artificial intelligence and the value of transparency. *AI Soc.* **36**, 585–595 (2021)
15. Wang, X., Yang, Y., Tao, D., Zhang, T.: The impact of AI transparency and reliability on human-AI collaborative decision-making. In: *Presented at the AHFE 2023 Hawaii Edition* (2023)
16. Gohel, P., Singh, P., Mohanty, M.: Explainable AI: current status and future directions
17. Letzgsus, S., Wagner, P., Lederer, J., Samek, W., Muller, K.-R., Montavon, G.: Toward explainable artificial intelligence for regression models: a methodological perspective. *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* **39**, 40–58 (2022)
18. Saeed, W., Omlin, C.: Explainable AI (XAI): a systematic meta-survey of current challenges and future opportunities. *Knowl. Based Syst.* **263**, 110273 (2023)
19. Janzing, D., Minorics, L., Blobaum, P.: Feature relevance quantification in explainable AI: a causal problem
20. Poché, A., Hervier, L., Bakkay, M.-C.: Natural example-based explainability: a survey. In: *Longo, L. (ed.) Explainable Artificial Intelligence*, pp. 24–47. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2023)
21. Gianfagna, L., Di Cecco, A.: Model-agnostic methods for XAI. In: *Explainable AI with Python*, pp. 81–113. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2021)

22. Zhang, K., Xu, P., Zhang, J.: Explainable AI in deep reinforcement learning models: a SHAP method applied in power system emergency control. In: 2020 IEEE 4th Conference on Energy Internet and Energy System Integration (EI2), pp. 711–716. IEEE, Wuhan, China (2020)
23. Nguyen, H.T.T., Cao, H.Q.: Evaluation of Explainable Artificial Intelligence: SHAP, LIME, and CAM
24. Müller, R., Reindel, D.F., Stadtfeld, Y.D.: The benefits and costs of explainable artificial intelligence in visual quality control: evidence from fault detection performance and eye movements. *Hum Ftrs Erg Mfg Svc.* (2024)
25. Alexander, Z., Chau, D.H., Saldaña, C.: An interrogative survey of explainable AI in manufacturing. *IEEE Trans. Ind. Inf.* **20**, 7069–7081 (2024)
26. Wang, Z., Liu, Y., Thiruselvi, A.A., Hamou-Lhadj, A.: XAIport: A Service Framework for the Early Adoption of XAI in AI Model Development (2024)
27. Zeng, Y., Chen, X., Jin, R.: Ensemble active learning by contextual bandits for AI incubation in manufacturing. *ACM Trans. Intell. Syst. Technol.* **15**, 1–26 (2024)
28. Song, Y., Li, F., Wang, Z., Zhang, B., Zhang, B.: Uncertainty quantification of data-driven quality prediction model for realizing the active sampling inspection of mechanical properties in steel production. *Int. J. Comput. Intell. Syst.* **17**, 74 (2024)
29. Johnson, M., Albizri, A., Harfouche, A., Fosso-Wamba, S.: Integrating human knowledge into artificial intelligence for complex and ill-structured problems: informed artificial intelligence. *Int. J. Inf. Manage.* **64**, 102479 (2022)
30. Powers, D.: Evaluation: from precision, recall and F-factor to ROC, informedness, markedness & correlation. *Mach. Learn. Technol.* **2** (2008)

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